

A Hybrid Handwritten Text Recognition Workflow: Evaluating Transkribus and eScriptorium in the Joseph Hooker Correspondence Project

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Despite growing in popularity during the 2000s, traditional Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technologies struggle with handwriting and historical fonts, especially on documents produced before the proliferation of typewriters in the early twentieth century [Nockels, Gooding and Terras 2024, 149-150]. In response to this, developments in Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR), especially over the past decade, have offered a rapidly evolving solution to cultural heritage professionals and researchers around the world as they seek to automate historical document transcription [Nockels et al. 2022]. The growing use of HTR tools in the galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM) sector today allows archivists and researchers to conveniently translate digital images of handwritten documents into machine-readable text [Terras 2022a]. In addition to making archival content more accessible, this process exposes manuscript corpora to a variety of digital research methods, from topic modelling to social network analysis.¹

This case study explores an open-source framework for HTR-assisted historical manuscript transcription in the context of academic and GLAM sector projects that rely on limited volunteer resources. How can cultural heritage institutions better utilize these platforms to create shareable HTR models? Focusing on the Transkribus and eScriptorium Virtual Research Environments (VREs), I assess the accuracy, transparency, and reproducibility of a generalizable workflow integrating both platforms [Kahle et al. 2017]; [Kiessling et al. 2019].

¹ What data is made accessible, and to whom, is an important question raised often in debates surrounding the appropriate implementation of FAIR and CARE data sharing principles [Carroll et al. 2021].

There are clear benefits to each VRE, and this project sought to draw on the strengths of both to test a novel volunteer workflow. Transkribus hosts a convenient web-based user interface, greater infrastructure for technical support, grants access to dedicated servers for model training and provides access to a large library of base models to aid in the HTR model training process. As the results of this project demonstrate, such base models can significantly improve the training of HTR models tailored to a specific individual's handwriting [Couture 2023, 10-11].

Similarly, open-source HTR models and repositories can reduce time and cost in historical document transcription, benefiting resource-limited archives and libraries and enabling wider public engagement. eScriptorium, a free and open-source software, offers additional flexibility in the export of models but requires more extensive technical background knowledge and local hosting capabilities to operate. Transkribus does not currently allow model exports, and any models made public can only be used within the web-based Transkribus platform. To support the development of public HTR model libraries, the final model created with eScriptorium was published via Zenodo and the HTR-United catalogue [Sicilia, García-Barriocanal and Sánchez-Alonso 2017]; [Chagué and Chiffolleau 2023]; [Schaefer and Litvine 2023]; [Romein et al. 2024].

This study assesses the advantages and disadvantages of implementing these platforms in a volunteer crowdsourcing workflow, using manuscripts from the Joseph Hooker Correspondence Project (JHCP) at the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.² Although Filosa [2025] compared the functionality of Transkribus and eScriptorium in a specific use case, no published literature at the time of writing directly compares the accuracy of Transkribus and eScriptorium HTR models trained on the same corpus. To address this, quantitative analysis of the error rates of HTR models trained on both platforms, along with anonymized

² <https://jdhooker.kew.org/p/jdh>

interviews and surveys with volunteers, were conducted to evaluate their real-world performance in a small-scale, volunteer-based project. This report first situates this 2023 pilot project within the JHCP and in relation to an earlier 2021-22 Transkribus pilot project at Kew. It then outlines primary methodologies and compares findings with the results of that preceding pilot project, proposing a hybrid Transkribus and eScriptorium workflow. The report concludes with a brief discussion of practical recommendations for improving the implementation of HTR technologies in similar use cases through the open-source sharing of ground truth training data and models.³

Background

The JHCP emerged from a 2011 partnership between the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew and the University of Sussex to produce digital images and full annotated transcriptions of Joseph Dalton Hooker's (1817-1911) correspondences while travelling around India from 1847-1851 [Centre for World Environmental History 2011]. For much of the past decade, the JHCP has relied on a volunteer transcription workflow in which volunteers would receive a letter image, transcribe it according to the project's protocols, and send it back to the Project Archivist for review. This time-consuming method of project management led to many initial transcribers either disliking the process or transcriptions that required substantial corrections. As a result, a small group of expert transcribers produced high-quality transcripts, but the opportunity for broader engagement with new volunteers remained limited. A high turnover rate of Project Archivists and inconsistent project funding have further added to the logistical challenges of maintaining a steady workflow for this small group of highly engaged volunteers [Gardner 2022a].

³ Ground truth data, in the context of machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI), refers to verified, accurate data used to train, validate, and test AI models [READ-COOP 2023b].

This 2023 case study stems directly from the work of the “Joseph Hooker and Transkribus Volunteer Pilot Project”, which ran from November 2021 to January 2022 and was led by then Project Archivist Rachael Gardner. During this period, a new remote volunteer workflow was tested, incorporating Transkribus. That trial project in turn built upon earlier projects, such as a 2020 model specifically trained on Joseph Hooker’s handwriting and the group work approach adopted by the Travelling Plants Volunteer Project based at the National Archives [Ross-Jones et al. 2023].⁴

The screenshot displays the eScriptorium web application interface. At the top, the navigation bar includes the eScriptorium logo, 'Home', 'Contact', 'My Projects', 'My Models', and 'Hello John'. Below this is a toolbar with various icons for navigation and editing. The main content area is divided into three panels:

- Left Panel:** A scanned image of a handwritten letter on aged paper. The text is written in cursive and is partially highlighted with a green selection box. A small green box in the top right corner of the image contains the text '(6A)'. A date stamp 'Roo 14/79' is visible in the top right of the image.
- Middle Panel:** A transcription of the handwritten text. The text is as follows:

Roo 14/79

Dear Dyer

t is too bad to
have to harass you as soon
As your back is tumes, but
Mr Mifford wants you
Olive with myself & Moore
at the Office at T. 30 Mr
on Monday.

Moore has sent in a weld
regmanole, full of utterly Jakse
statements.

I hop Harret bove the
goumey well with love to hes
sve be Y2

JD Hooker
- Right Panel:** A list of line numbers corresponding to the transcription, numbered 1 through 18.

⁴ This initial “Joseph_Hooker_v1.0” HTR model was trained by the author in 2020 as a Joseph Hooker Correspondence Project Remote Intern, funded by the Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology.

Figure 1. Screenshot of Joseph Hooker's handwriting in the eScriptorium (top) and Transkribus (bottom) web-based user interfaces [18 April 2023].

The volunteer workflow implemented in this 2021-22 pilot project aimed to enhance inclusivity and accessibility through various measures. Primarily, in asking volunteers to process machine-generated transcripts, the project was designed to be less intimidating than transcribing a letter onto a blank page. As a remote project, this workflow welcomed individuals who couldn't physically access Kew, allowing a broader range of participants and trying not to cater exclusively to a UK audience. Furthermore, previous experience transcribing manuscripts was not required for volunteers to participate [Gardner 2022a]. To account for variations in technical knowledge, the project maintained comprehensive volunteer protocols, which formed the basis for the Transkribus guidance and protocols used in the 2023 study [Appendix A].

The 2021-22 pilot project received 71 complete applications from a diverse pool of volunteers including individuals who had previously volunteered for Kew, academics, biologists, retirees, archive students, and stay-at-home parents seeking career changes. Applicants spanned countries such as the UK, US, India, China, Italy, Germany, Switzerland,

and Nigeria, showcasing the global reach of the project. To prioritize inclusivity and accessibility, the project managers decided not to prioritize certain candidates over others based on their academic backgrounds or other factors, and all applicants progressed. Throughout the project, a total of nine volunteers withdrew for various reasons, including technical problems, health issues, time constraints, commitments to other volunteer projects, and loss of interest. The remaining volunteers demonstrated a wide range of time commitment to the project [Gardner 2022a].

The Hooker Collection itself is also heterogeneous, encompassing primarily letters (both personal and professional), and copies of these correspondences in several hands and formats, along with related material such as newspaper clippings and plant exchange logs. At least 21% of the letters are typescript/typewritten (as opposed to manuscript/handwritten), and some of the manuscripts are in a hand other than Hooker's. Due in part to this irregularity of the collection material, the 2021-22 pilot project drew upon a mix of previously untranscribed handwritten and typescript letters. Because the general "Transkribus Print M1" model for typescript proved more reliable than either the initial 2020 "Joseph_Hooker_v1.0" or "Transkribus English Handwriting M3" HTR models, there was a slight bias towards typewritten letters during the project.⁵ A total of 360 letters, both manuscript and typescript, were transcribed by 60-70 remote volunteers working in small groups [Gardner 2022a].

The workflow implemented in the pilot project clearly demonstrated increased output and volunteer engagement relative to the previous fully manual transcription system. However, Gardner emphasized that it did not eliminate the need for a Project Archivist or allow for a more hands-off approach to volunteer management. Significant time and effort

⁵ The 2020 Transkribus "Joseph_Hooker_v1.0" HTR model was originally trained with CITIab HTR+ engine developed at the University of Rostock in 2017 but had to be retrained on PyLaia – an open-source HTR engine which is now the core engine in Transkribus – at the beginning of this study in 2022. The retrained version, "Joseph_Hooker_v2.0", was used in this project. See [Puigcerver 2017]; [Heigl 2020].

were required to prepare letters, track group progress, upload letters to Transkribus, run models, and communicate with volunteers. Feedback from volunteers emphasized their appreciation for the engagement and support provided by the Project Archivist while also highlighting areas where additional guidance, such as specific sessions on formatting, would have been beneficial [Gardner 2022a]. By limiting the number of participants on this project and only advertising to a pool of previous participants, most of whom had participated in the pilot project, I sought to maintain similar levels of support despite being both a full-time graduate student and project manager, recognizing regular communication as crucial to volunteer engagement.

Gardner noted several additional challenges that arose from the project's commitment to accessibility that I attempted to remedy by limiting the scope of this study. Not requiring a set time commitment made group work more difficult, and the absence of prior experience or skills necessitated extensive project support and technical assistance. Project feedback revealed that strong volunteer engagement and support were crucial for effectively involving a more diverse group of volunteers [Gardner 2022a]. In this workflow, a balance had to be struck between accessibility and self-support, recognizing that both objectives could not be fully achieved simultaneously. Nevertheless, the project's achievements and scale indicated that a remote volunteer workflow was worth further investigation.

Suggested improvements included enhancing communication and collaboration within groups, addressing challenges related to downloading text files from Transkribus, managing files in OneDrive, streamlining the formatting aspect of the workflow, and providing focused group demonstrations on transcription and formatting. Gardner also noted that the inclusion of more typescript letters, which had a higher accuracy rate and may have been easier for some volunteers, could have increased project outputs [Gardner 2022a]. However, reducing the focus on handwritten letters may have conversely reduced the

engagement of those who enjoyed the challenge and specialist knowledge required of transcription, based on volunteer feedback. Foregrounding volunteer expertise was essential in developing a more nuanced workflow for the 2023 project (Figure 3). This supports calls from across the sciences and humanities to better recognize and acknowledge the volunteer labor that serves as the bedrock of many digitization initiatives [Romein et al. 2024]; [Enright and Smith 2025].

Methods

During their tenure as Project Archivist, Gardner compiled important statistics on the scope of the collection for the first time and the progress of transcription efforts. Of the 5,787 nonblank letters that make up the Joseph Hooker Collection within the Kew Library and Archives, 5,729 letters (99%) have been scanned and digitised as of April 2022. As there has not been a Project Archivist in post since then, progress has stalled: only 26% of the collection has been uploaded to the Joseph Hooker Collection website, and 13% of letters are currently searchable with complete transcriptions and metadata. These are usually corrected by a Kew archivist [Gardner 2022b].

The precise number of un-transcribed pages is not known, but it is possible to estimate that the collection contains roughly 22,800 to 28,800 pages of material relevant to Joseph Hooker (mostly correspondence).⁶ Even accounting for the backlog of nearly 750 uncorrected letters that will require review before being added to the website, as many as 16,000 to 21,000 pages remain un-transcribed [Gardner 2022b]. At the current pace of the project, transcribing these documents manually is a monumental task. Acknowledging the

⁶ 1,491 letters (5,938 pages) have been uploaded to the Joseph Hooker Collection website, and 759 letters (3,744 pages) were searchable with complete transcriptions and metadata as of May 2023. However, many of these letters are from Hooker's 1847-1851 travels around India and are significantly lengthier than the often more administrative correspondence written during his tenure as Director of Kew. This likely inflated my estimates.

difficulties of the current funding climate, automating aspects of the transcription process for a collection of this size is vital to making its contents accessible to researchers globally. The JHCP presents an ideal opportunity to experiment with novel transcription workflows.

The 2023 study focused on implementing a novel crowdsourcing transcription workflow that integrated Transkribus as a front-end VRE for volunteers and eScriptorium for back-end open-source model training (Figure 3).⁷ Originally, the project was to be hosted entirely on eScriptorium, but due to logistical difficulties in securing suitable server space, the workflow was divided between the two platforms. A small team of seven volunteers participated in this two-month initiative from March to May 2023. All volunteers attended an online introductory meeting via Microsoft Teams, which included a detailed walkthrough of the transcription workflow and a Transkribus demonstration. They were then given access to the project OneDrive folder, which included the Joseph Hooker Correspondence Project Volunteer Protocols (v2.1), modified from the pilot project protocols developed by Project Archivist Rachael Gardner, a spreadsheet of known acquaintances of Hooker, a visual alphabet of Hooker's handwriting, and Project Tracker spreadsheet (Figure 2) [Appendix A].

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
	Archive Reference	Transcriber initials	Date assigned	Date transcript completed	Transcript checked initials	Transcript checked date	Transcript complete?	Notes/Comments
1	JDH/2/16/65	RXB	8/3/2023	9/3/2023 JS		10/3/2023	yes	
2	JDH/2/16/66	CW	8/3/2023	12/3/2023 JS		19/3/2023	yes	
3	JDH/2/16/67	RXB	9/3/2023	10/3/2023 JS		10/3/2023	yes	
4	JDH/2/16/67a	RXB	9/3/2023	12/3/2023 JS		19/3/2023	yes	
5	JDH/2/16/68	RXB	12/3/2023	15/3/2023 JS		19/3/2023	yes	
6	JDH/2/16/69	RXB	9/3/2023	13/3/2023 JS		20/3/2023	yes	
7	JDH/2/16/70	RXB	10/3/2023	14/3/2023 JS		3/4/2023	yes	
8	JDH/2/16/71	CW	10/3/2023	12/3/2023 JS		13/3/2023	yes	
9	JDH/2/16/72	RXB	12/3/2023	16/3/2023 JS		3/4/2023	yes	Page 7 looks out of place - the writing on
10	JDH/2/16/73	CEF	11/3/2023	15/03/2023 JS		23/3/2023	yes	
11	JDH/2/16/74	CW	12/3/2023	13/3/23 JS		4/4/2023	yes	
12	JDH/2/16/75	RXB	14/3/2023	16/3/2023 JS		4/4/2023	yes	
13	JDH/2/16/76	RXB	15/3/2023	20/3/2023 JS		4/4/2023	yes	The transcribed letter on the website mi
14	JDH/2/16/77	CW	13/03/23	14/3/23 JS		5/4/2023	yes	

Figure 2. Project Tracker in shared group OneDrive. See Appendix A for full Volunteer Protocols.

The general workflow of this study was divided into two phases. During Phase One, volunteers were asked to correct transcriptions generated by a Transkribus HTR model

⁷ This project was organized in collaboration with Cambridge Digital Humanities and Kew archivists Kiri Ross-Jones and Isabel Lauterjung.

trained on approximately 20,000 words from a corpus of letters between Joseph Dalton Hooker (1817-1911) and his son-in-law and successor as Director of Kew, William Thiselton-Dyer (1843-1928). This series was chosen because it is composed almost entirely of handwritten documents, saving the time of manually sorting out stray typewritten correspondence. Volunteers proceeded to correct 37 letters (approximately 100 pages or 15,000 words of text) over the course of March and April 2023 (Figure 4). These transcriptions were then used to train a series of updated models, both with and without the use of a Transkribus base model (Table 1).

Phase Two focused on applying the updated model to previously un-transcribed correspondence from the Joseph Hooker Collection. Two smaller groups of letters and manuscript drafts (totaling 22 pages or approximately 5,000 words) from the miscellaneous manuscripts (QX) series were selected: one focusing on the construction of the Kew (King's) Observatory and another on enlarging the local church. Some of the draft letters remained challenging to transcribe even with the help of the updated HTR model (Table 1). The poor quality of some pages, which had been heavily edited with many sections crossed out and rewritten, impacted the accuracy of the final models on both Transkribus and eScriptorium. The manual correction of Transkribus-generated baselines and the volunteer-corrected transcriptions constituted a significant time investment at this stage, and ground truth data cleaning concluded in May 2023.

Corresponding eScriptorium models were trained locally at regular intervals on datasets of roughly 20, 35, and 40 thousand words throughout the project (Table 1). At each of these intervals, Extensible Markup Language (XML) files downloaded from Transkribus ensured that the models on both platforms were trained on identical ground truth training sets. Beyond assessing the accuracy of these platforms in practice, it is important to note that this aspect of the project was not focused on maximizing the number of letters transcribed, but

rather on improving the size of the training set and thus the accuracy of the models on both platforms, as well as working to gauge the sentiment of a small group of volunteer transcribers using these technologies [Schaefer forthcoming 2026].

Training the eScriptorium models also posed technical challenges. As a computationally intensive process, my personal laptop (16 GB RAM) could not effectively train models on even a relatively small sample of a few pages. Therefore, all training took place on an external computer (32 GB RAM) housed at the University of Cambridge History Faculty. The final eScriptorium model and training dataset are currently available through Zenodo and the HTR-United repository [Schaefer and Litvine 2023]. Corrected and reformatted transcriptions of the letters are in the process of being published on the JHCP website hosted by Kew.⁸ Figure 3 illustrates a suggested workflow generalizable to similarly heterogeneous corpora based on volunteer feedback gathered throughout this project.

Figure 3. Suggested workflow for HTR model improvement and transcription with a corpus of both typescript and manuscript documents. By the author.

⁸ <https://jdhooker.kew.org/p/jdh>

Transkribus launched its next generation of “Super Models” a month after the conclusion of this project in June 2023 [READ-COOP 2023a]. Super Models are advanced, pre-trained text recognition models designed to deliver highly accurate transcriptions across heterogeneous document collections without requiring users to train their own models. Unlike traditional PyLaia models—which excel with highly specific datasets—Super Models are built using “transformer-based” text recognition technology and trained on large multilingual datasets of both printed and handwritten texts. This makes them ideal for transcribing archives with mixed languages, styles, or formats.⁹ PyLaia models may still outperform in narrowly defined tasks, but Super Models currently offer better performance “out of the box” for broader use cases [READ-COOP 2023a].

Examples of these models available on Transkribus include the Text Titan, applicable to most Latin text scripts, alongside language-specific Super Models like the Dutch Dean and English Elder. The latest version, “Text Titan Iter” was trained on 31,127,219 words from 10+ Latin language corpora and released to Transkribus subscribers 11 June 2025, outperforming many leading Large Language Models (LLMs) [Noble 2025]. However, Super Models are at the time of writing only available to Transkribus users with subscription plans, with the option to test the models during a 7-day free trial period [Park 2025]. They also cannot be used as base models for training in Transkribus at this time. Therefore, in the interest of focusing on the production of sharable models with minimal barriers to access, the workflow outlined in Figure 3 refers only to the public typescript OCR and manuscript HTR options available in Transkribus without a subscription.

⁹ A transformer is a neural network architecture that relies heavily on a mechanism called self-attention, which allows the model to weigh the importance of different parts of the input data. Unlike older models that processed text or images in sequence (step-by-step), transformers can analyze the whole input at once, capturing long-range relationships more efficiently [Li et al. 2022]; [Vaswani et al. 2023].

Ethics

Ethical concerns encompassing privacy, informed consent, and intellectual property are vital considerations in a project of this nature, which involves highly collaborative outputs [Romein et al. 2024]. To address these concerns and improve transparency, all volunteers signed a comprehensive “Virtual/Remote Volunteering Agreement” as mandated by Kew. The document provides volunteers with the option to consent to the sharing of their email information with other volunteers and explicitly states that volunteers shall “Assign to Kew any copyright or other intellectual property rights that might result from your volunteering role and give permission for any resultant documentation (e.g. transcriptions) to be published/used by Kew.” [Appendix B] All personal identifying information was safely secured in a password-protected Kew SharePoint folder. To address any additional privacy concerns, transparent email communication and an open “Question & Answer” session were also provided.

Regarding the collection, storage, and long-term preservation of data, all volunteer information is securely stored in a password-protected Kew SharePoint folder, and email correspondences are transmitted using a secure Kew email platform. Feedback surveys were distributed via Microsoft Forms, and interviews were carried out via a Kew Microsoft Teams account. Interviews were recorded with explicit consent and removed from Kew OneDrive after 12 months. Volunteers were given the option to be formally recognized for their contributions as co-creators of the transcripts, or to remain anonymous, with all choosing the latter option citing privacy concerns. A summary of ethical considerations for this project was submitted to the University of Cambridge English Faculty and Kew Library and Archives for approval before survey and interview data were collected.

Results

The quantitative metrics for measuring the accuracy of models generated on both Transkribus and eScriptorium were Character Error Rate (CER) and Word Error Rate (WER).

Transkribus calculated both CER and WER based on a random “validation set” of ground truth transcriptions (5% of pages) separated from the complete “training set” of letters as the model was generated. eScriptorium estimated CER on a randomized selection of the training set. The CER and WER for both final models on eScriptorium and Transkribus were verified manually using a page of ground truth correspondence that was set aside from both training and validation sets, with an average 2% CER (Transkribus and eScriptorium) and 5% WER (Transkribus) margin of error determined at the time of training (Table 1).

Table 1. Character Error Rate (CER), Word Error Rate (WER) performance and training data for all project HTR models.

<i>Description</i>	<i>Average CER (%)</i>	<i>Best WER (%)</i>	<i>Words in Training Set</i>	<i>Date</i>
Transkribus English Handwriting M3 (Base Model)	5.10	-	2 125 253	16/10/2021
Transkribus w/ Base Model 1	10.7	30.4	19 973	08/03/2023
Transkribus w/ Base Model 2	11.1	30.3	34 329	12/04/2023
Transkribus w/ Base Model 3	10.7	28.5	40 029	11/05/2023
Transkribus w/ Base Model 4 (post data cleaning)	8.5	25.3	38 445	14/05/2023
Transkribus 1	17.9	46.7	19 973	08/03/2023

Transkribus 2	15.5	38	34 874	12/04/2023
Transkribus 3	16.0	40.7	38 319	11/05/2023
Transkribus 4 (post data cleaning)	11.9	30.2	39 749	23/05/2023
eScriptorium 1	20.6	-	19 973	02/12/2022
eScriptorium 2	15.6	-	34 874	18/04/2023
eScriptorium 3 (training failed, likely due to incorrectly exported XML files)	-	-	-	19/05/2023
eScriptorium 4 (post data cleaning)	11.1	-	40 029	26/05/2023

Character Error Rates (CER)

Figure 4. Comparison of CER rates of Transkribus and eScriptorium HTR models, with incrementally larger training sets updated over the course of the two-month volunteer project. By the author.

Figure 5. Final Joseph Hooker HTR model train/validation CER *with* Transkribus base model (right) and *without* (left). Images courtesy of Transkribus [1 June 2023].

Despite doubling the size of the training set, improvement to the Transkribus model was marginal. As expected, the gap between Transkribus models trained with and without the base model closed slightly with the larger training set, but the base model still consistently provided a roughly 5% increase in accuracy. However, increasing the size of the training set had a more significant impact on the accuracy of models trained with eScriptorium’s Kraken engine. Manual cleaning of both baselines and transcripts resulted in an improved CER of 8.5% and WER of 25.3% on Transkribus (Table 1). However, the difference between eScriptorium and Transkribus CERs quickly became marginal (1-2%) when trained without a base model (Figure 4). This finding supports the use of eScriptorium as an effective open-source alternative to Transkribus.

Qualitative data was gathered through both surveys and interviews. The 2021-22 pilot project received 27 feedback survey responses from a pool of approximately 60 active volunteers. Participants in the project had diverse motivations for joining, encompassing interests in botany and history, the inability to volunteer at their usual organization due to the pandemic, the desire to acquire new skills to enhance employability, and the opportunity to

utilize Transkribus software. One volunteer reportedly found the task more akin to “solving a crossword puzzle,” making it both accessible and enjoyable [Gardner 2022a]. However, the overarching motivation seemed to be a strong sense of connection to Kew and a genuine desire to support the organization. Some key concerns voiced by pilot respondents informed the design of this project. These included complaints regarding working in groups, transferring files from Transkribus to OneDrive, and the complexity of the guidance and protocols.

2021-22 volunteer feedback regarding Transkribus was generally positive, despite some critical comments. Initially, volunteers were surprised by the machine reading's inaccuracy, but their confidence grew as they became more familiar with using the technology. The Project Archivist's preparation of images and running of layout and text recognition models before granting access to volunteers made the transcription process within Transkribus relatively self-contained and intuitive. However, challenges arose when the transcript moved from Transkribus to other stages of the workflow. A major complication in the project workflow was transferring the transcript from Transkribus to the shared group OneDrive and formatting the transcription in a Word document, including moving it between folders within OneDrive. To account for this, the new Transkribus/eScriptorium project adopted a more streamlined approach in which all volunteer transcription took place within the Transkribus online VRE, with volunteers accessing the collection of letters through personal Transkribus accounts.

Of the original seven participants, four were active throughout the project, one left to pursue traditional transcription of another series in the Hooker Collection that they were more familiar with, one left due to academic commitments, and one left for personal reasons. The survey received five anonymous responses. Opinions of the new workflow were mixed, with some volunteers appreciating the simplified instructions and more self-guided procedures,

and others requesting a return to collaborative group work, highlighting the importance of volunteering as part of a community. I had initially planned to set up a collaborative workspace for the volunteers but decided not to do so when some expressed privacy concerns. Additionally, the volunteers self-reported spending a total of 45-50 hours on the project. Three 30-minute semi-structured interviews with volunteers were conducted following the conclusion of the project. The critical and theoretical implications of these volunteer dialogues will be discussed in a forthcoming book chapter [Schaefer forthcoming 2026].

HTR-United [Home](#) [Browse the Catalog](#) [Record New Data](#) [Models](#)

Joseph Hooker HTR

Joseph Hooker Correspondence Project 1850 - 1911

[Link](#) Data repository

Language eng Script Latn Script Type only-manuscript Hands 1

 Volume 337 pages

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 Software Transkribus

XML transcriptions and JPEG images exported from Transkribus as ground truth for an eScriptorium-Kraken HTR model (CER 11-12%) trained on the correspondence of Joseph Dalton Hooker (1817-1911), primarily letters to William Turner Thiselton-Dyer (1843-1928) during the late-19th/early-20th century. Many transcriptions in this dataset were generated by a small team of anonymous volunteers as part of the Joseph Hooker Correspondence Project based at Kew Gardens. All images in this dataset are reproduced with the kind permission of the Board of Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens Kew (© RBG, Kew). Contact archives@kew.org for more information.

HTR Model: Schaefer, John, & Litvine, Alexis. (2023). Joseph Hooker HTR Model. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8038689>

Authors: John, Schaefer and Kiri, Ross-Jones and Alexis, Litvine

[Complete record](#) [# Tweet](#)

Figure 6. ‘Joseph Hooker HTR’ model entry in the HTR-United catalogue [4 June 2024]. Platforms like HTR-United, powered by Github, and Zenodo offer options for sharing HTR models and training data with the broader research community.

Discussion

Today, Transkribus remains an incredibly powerful resource for the academic community yet is a fundamentally closed and centralized system whereas eScriptorium presents an open-

source and decentralized alternative, with a growing community support base.¹⁰ While Transkribus has expanded its public base models to include new non-Latin scripts, archives and independent researchers seeking to fine-tune these base models on specific corpora are still unable to export their models and must pay subscription fees to access more accurate transformer-based Super Models. Until this system changes, open-source platforms like eScriptorium remain the most promising option for researchers and archives seeking to freely share their HTR models. As the results of this case study show, once a sufficient training dataset is available, the difference between the two platforms in terms of accuracy and efficiency becomes marginal (Figure 4). These project findings demonstrate that integrating HTR tools into crowdsourcing workflows is a cost-effective strategy for smaller transcription projects to generate (re)usable HTR models and employ them for collaborative manuscript transcription within a limited timeframe. The new Joseph Hooker model can now be used in future iterations of the JHCP as well as by individual volunteers and researchers in the absence of a Project Archivist at Kew.

Furthermore, this workflow is ideal for the open-source publication of the resulting models and ground truth data; contributing to a more diverse repository of base models that significantly reduces the amount of initial training material required to produce accurate and generalizable models in future resource-limited projects. In order to render HTR technology accessible to the widest range of GLAM institutions and researchers possible, aiming to (responsibly) make training datasets available to the larger research community is a critical consideration of such projects [Romein et al. 2024].

Following the conclusion of this project in 2023, the resulting ground truth data published via GitHub, Zenodo, and HTR-United has been used to support other experiments

¹⁰ For further discussion of the Transkribus and READ-COOP business model see [Terras 2022a]; [Terras 2022b]; [Terras et al. 2025].

in automated text recognition [Chagué and Scheithauer 2024]; [Chen and Ströbel 2024]. The “Joseph Hooker HTR” model has been viewed 203 times and downloaded 29 times from Zenodo as of 15 July 2025 [Schaefer and Litvine 2023]. Overall, the findings of this study support the practical viability of a shift towards a more open-source HTR research ecosystem by leveraging hybrid implementations of both the Transkribus and eScriptorium VREs, especially for small-scale, resource-limited projects that rely heavily on volunteer labor.

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